

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF DIABETIC FOOT (UNHEALING WOUND): A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Diabetic Foot Ulcer (DFU) is a challenging complication of long-standing diabetes, often resistant to healing due to neuropathy, ischemia, and infection. A 60-year-old female patient with a chronic non-healing wound on the right foot for 3 months was treated with Ayurvedic Shodhana and Ropana modalities including Triphala Kashaya, Panchavalkala Kwatha, Jatyadi Taila, Haridra-Guduchi Churna, and internal Rasayana therapy. Markable improvement was observed with reduction in wound size, discharge, pain, smell, and formation of healthy granulation tissue. **Conclusion:** Ayurvedic treatment shows safe and effective wound healing potential in diabetic foot ulcers.

KEYWORDS: Diabetic Foot, Dushta Vrana, Jatyadi Taila, Triphala, Ayurveda, Case Study.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes Mellitus reduces wound healing capacity because of neuropathy, microangiopathy and compromised immunity. Chronic wounds are categorized in Ayurveda under Dushta Vrana, characterized by:

- Slow healing
- Slough
- Foul smell

- Discharge
- Color changes
- Pain

Sushruta emphasizes Vrana Shodhana and Vrana Ropana for effective healing. Ayurvedic local and systemic therapies address infection, inflammation, tissue repair, and overall immunity.

NEED OF STUDY

- Diabetic foot ulcers are rising due to increased diabetes prevalence.
- Modern care is costly, slow, and has recurrence risk.
- Ayurveda provides affordable, safe and holistic healing without side effects.

AIM

To evaluate the effect of Ayurvedic treatment in a non-healing diabetic foot wound.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study wound healing using Ayurvedic Shodhana and Ropana measures.
2. To observe changes in wound size, discharge, pain, granulation.
3. To assess systemic improvement and glycemic stability.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Case Description

A 60-year-old female patient with:

- Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus (12 years)
- Chronic non-healing ulcer on right foot for 3 months
- Pain, discharge, foul smell, blackish discoloration
- Difficulty walking

History

- Ulcer started after minor trauma
- Received antibiotics and dressings without improvement
- Wound gradually increased
- Came for Ayurvedic management

Local Examination (Vrana)

- Size: 5 cm × 4 cm
- Slough: Present
- Granulation: Poor
- Exudate: Moderate
- Smell: Foul
- Margins: Irregular
- Pain: ++

Systemic Findings

- Elevated blood sugar
- Mild neuropathy
- Reduced sensation on plantar aspect

TREATMENT PLAN**1. Vrana Shodhana (Purification)**

- Triphala Kashaya wash – BID
- Panchavalkala Kwatha – alternate days
- Removal of slough (soft debridement)

2. Vrana Ropana (Healing)

- Jatyadi Taila dressing – daily
- Haridra + Guduchi Churna – 2 g BID
- Kaishore Guggulu – 2 tablets BID
- Triphala Guggulu – 2 tablets HS

3. Systemic Therapy

- Guduchi Satva – 500 mg BID
- Nisha–Amalaki – BID
- Chandraprabha Vati – BID

Diet & Lifestyle

- Avoid sweets, fermented, junk, oily food
- Warm water
- Blood sugar monitoring

- Foot care instructions

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Symptom	Before Treatment	After 15 Days	After 30 Days
Pain	+++	++	+
Discharge	+++	+	–
Foul smell	++	+	–
Burning	++	+	–
Walking difficulty	+++	++	+

OBJECTIVE

Parameter	Before Treatment	After Treatment
Slough	Present	Absent
Granulation	Poor	Healthy, red
Margins	Irregular	Healthy margins
Exudate	Moderate	Minimal

RESULTS

- Significant reduction in wound size
- Complete disappearance of foul smell
- Healthy granulation tissue developed
- Slough cleared completely
- Patient able to walk comfortably
- Improvement in glycemetic control

DISCUSSION

Ayurvedic treatment works through:

1. Shodhana

Triphala and Panchavalkala act as antiseptic, anti-inflammatory, and cleansing agents.

2. Ropana

Jatyadi Taila accelerates connective tissue formation, reduces inflammation, and promotes epithelialization.

3. Rasayana & Raktashodhaka

Guduchi, Haridra, Guggulu formulations purify blood, increase immunity, and improve glucose metabolism.

4. Systemic Correction

Nisha-Amalaki controls glucose → improves healing capacity.

Thus, Ayurveda effectively manages Dushta Vrana even in diabetic patients.

CONCLUSION

Ayurvedic management of diabetic foot using Shodhana & Ropana therapy shows:

- Fast wound healing
- Reduction in infection & pain
- Healthy granulation
- Improved foot function

This approach is holistic, economical, minimally invasive, and prevents complications.

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